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Distributed Guidance Law for Containment Maneuvering of Underactuated Surface Vehicles

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Abstract—In this paper, we propose a distributed guidance method for the containment maneuvering of multiple underactuated unmanned surface vehicles in the presence of ocean currents. In the proposed approach, consensus algorithms are first introduced to generate reference paths and synchronize the vehicles. Then, nonlinear surge and heading guidance laws are designed to ensure the convergence to the desired path and compensate for the sideslip effect. The effectiveness of the proposed approach is verified by numerical simulations.

Index Terms—Containment control, USVs, ocean currents, ILOS guidance, path-following, sideslip compensation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The last few decades have witnessed significant developments in the cooperative control of networked unmanned surface vehicles (USVs), driven by their growing importance in various maritime applications, including ocean surveillance, resource transportation, and coordinated search and rescue operations [1]. The fundamental concept of multi-vehicle coordination is to utilize cost-effective, simple, and compact marine vehicles instead of relying on a single expensive, specialized vehicle. By working together, these vehicles can perform complex tasks that a single vehicle usually cannot, even when equipped with advanced technology [2]. Aiming to accomplish complex missions using a fleet of surface vehicles, extensive research has been conducted on cooperative control strategies, including rendezvous, formation, and containment control [3].

One significant issue in multi-vehicle coordination is to attain and maintain a predefined formation pattern, allowing multiple vehicles to work together to complete a given task. Various formation control strategies have been developed to accomplish this, including behavior-based control [4], virtual structures [5], and the leader-follower framework [6]–[8]. Among these, the single leader-follower approach is widely favored in ocean engineering applications due to its simplicity and scalability. However, in the USV formation systems examined in these studies, followers depend heavily on the leader. If the leader collides with obstacles and is damaged, the followers lose their reference signal and cannot

complete their tasks. Thus, while effective, the single leader-follower approach may not be suitable for complex tasks requiring high reliability [9].

In recent years, significant efforts have been devoted to increasing USV formation system robustness and reliability by involving multiple leaders guidance. With multiple leaders in USVs formation system, followers can rely on an undamaged leader's information to complete tasks [9], [10]. In this context, the containment control approach has emerged as a widely studied topic, focusing on guiding followers into the convex hull spanned by multiple leaders [11]. Various containment control schemes have been proposed in the literature. For instance, in [11] and [12] a distributed containment controller for surface vehicles is proposed, where each USV is subject to uncertain dynamics and unknown disturbances. In [13], a containment controller is designed for underwater vehicles, where the model uncertainties are approximated using predictor-based neural networks (NNs). Although these studies employ different control strategies, they commonly assume that the surge and sway velocities of USV are known, which necessitates the use of expensive sensors.

In this paper, we propose a distributed guidance method for the containment maneuvering of multiple underactuated unmanned surface vehicles in the presence of ocean currents. The proposed approach employs consensus algorithms to synchronize path variables and generate reference paths for each follower within the convex hull spanned by the leaders. Furthermore, nonlinear surge and heading guidance laws are designed to ensure convergence to the desired paths and compensate for the sideslip effect. Unlike [11]–[13], the proposed method relies on an estimation approach for sideslip compensation rather than using direct velocity measurements. The effectiveness of the proposed method is demonstrated through numerical experiments.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II presents preliminaries and defines the containment maneuvering problem, while Section III introduces the proposed algorithm. Section IV presents simulation results, and Section V concludes the paper.

II. PRELIMINARIES AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

Consider a networked system of multiple USVs depicted in Fig 1. Vehicles labeled from 1 to N act as followers. They are guided by M virtual leaders that move along predefined parameterized paths, labeled from $N + 1$ to $N + M$.

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The three degrees of freedom kinematic model of i th USV is given as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_i = u_i \cos \psi_i - v_i \sin \psi_i, \\ \dot{y}_i = u_i \sin \psi_i + v_i \cos \psi_i, \\ \dot{\psi}_i = r_i, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $p_i = [x_i(t), y_i(t)]^T$ and ψ_i are the position and orientation of the i -th USV relative to the North-East-Down frame $\{n\}$; u_i , v_i , and r_i denote the linear surge and sway velocities, and angular yaw rate in the body-fixed frame $\{b\}$, respectively, where $i = 1, \dots, N$ [14]. The communication among USVs and virtual leaders is described by a directed graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{A})$, where $\mathcal{V} = \{v_1, \dots, v_{N+M}\}$ is the set of nodes, $\mathcal{E} \subseteq \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$ is the set of edges, and $\mathcal{A} = [a_{ij}] \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+M) \times (N+M)}$ is the weighted adjacency matrix of the graph \mathcal{G} . The motion of leaders is assumed to be independent of that of followers, and their paths are denoted by $p_k(\theta_k) = [x_k(\theta_k), y_k(\theta_k)]^T$, where $k = N+1, \dots, N+M$, and $\theta_k(t)$ is a path variable. It is also assumed that each follower has at least one neighbor, while leaders do not communicate among themselves and do not receive information from followers. Due to this fact, the Laplacian matrix $\mathcal{L} = [l_{ij}] \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+M) \times (N+M)}$ associated with \mathcal{A} can be partitioned in the following way

$$\mathcal{L} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{L}_1 & \mathcal{L}_2 \\ 0_{M \times N} & 0_{M \times M} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{L}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, $\mathcal{L}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$ [12], [15].

Assumption 1: Each follower has at least one leader that has a path to that follower.

Assumption 2: All leaders share the same path variable, i.e., $\theta_k(t) = \theta_0(t)$ for all $k = N+1, \dots, N+M$, and it evolves at a constant rate $\dot{\theta}_0 = \nu_s$.

The control objective is to design the guidance algorithm for each follower based on its local information and the information acquired through their neighbours such that:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} |p_i(t) - p_{di}(\theta_0)| \leq \delta, \quad (3)$$

where δ is a positive constant, and $p_{di} = [x_{di}(\theta_0), y_{di}(\theta_0)]^T$ denotes the reference path of follower i , which satisfies

$$P_d(\theta_0) = -(\mathcal{L}_1^{-1} \mathcal{L}_2 \otimes I_2) X_L(\theta_0), \quad (4)$$

where $P_d(\theta_0) = [p_{d1}^T(\theta_0), \dots, p_{dN}^T(\theta_0)]^T$ and $X_L(\theta_0) = [p_{N+1}^T(\theta_0), \dots, p_{N+M}^T(\theta_0)]^T$, while the symbol \otimes represents the Kronecker product, and I_2 is the identity matrix of dimension 2.

Remark 1: The set of points $P_d(\theta_0)$, as defined in Eq. (4), represents a convex combination of the leaders' positions at time t , provided that Assumption 1 holds [13], [16].

III. PROPOSED COOPERATIVE GUIDANCE LAW

In this section, we propose a distributed guidance law for containment maneuvering. In the first part, we describe the consensus algorithm for generating reference paths and synchronizing the vehicles' path variables. Subsequently, we design guidance laws for each vehicle to achieve the objective (3).

Fig. 1: Containment maneuvering geometry.

A. Reference points generation and synchronization

Due to communication constraints, the path information (4) is not available in advance to the followers. To estimate the reference path to be followed, each vehicle uses the following consensus protocol:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{p}}_{di}(\theta_0) = & -\gamma \left(\sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} (\hat{p}_{di}(\theta_0) - \hat{p}_{dj}(\theta_0)) \right. \\ & \left. + \sum_{j=N+1}^{N+M} a_{ij} (\hat{p}_{di}(\theta_0) - p_j(\theta_0)) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $i = 1, \dots, N$, $\gamma > 0$ is a constant, and $\hat{p}_{di} = [\hat{x}_{di}(\theta_0), \hat{y}_{di}(\theta_0)]^T$ is an current estimation of p_{di} . It should be noted that, under the dynamics of (5), $\hat{p}_{di}(\theta_0)$ will follow $p_{di}(\theta_0)$ with an accuracy that depends on the parameter γ [17].

Using (5), the vehicle obtains only its reference position, but the direction in which it should move remains unknown. This information is contained in the first partial derivative of the path p_{di} with respect to θ_0 . To estimate it, we also use the consensus algorithm as follows:

$$\dot{\hat{p}}'_{di} = -\gamma \left(\sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} (\hat{p}'_{di} - \hat{p}'_{dj}) + \sum_{j=N+1}^{N+M} a_{ij} (\hat{p}'_{di} - p'_j) \right), \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{p}'_{di} = \partial \hat{p}_{di} / \partial \theta_0$ is the estimate of $p'_{di} = \partial p_{di} / \partial \theta_0$, while $p'_j = \partial p_j / \partial \theta_0$.

Finally, it is assumed that the leaders' path variable θ_0 is not known to all followers. In order to ensure that the i th USV has complete information about its reference path, we use additional consensus protocol to synchronize path variables:

$$\dot{\theta}_i = -\gamma \sum_{j=1}^{N+1} a_{ij} (\theta_i - \theta_j), \quad (7)$$

where $i = 1, \dots, N$. Taking Assumption 2 into account, we conclude that $\hat{\theta}_i$ will converge to ν_s , i.e., $\theta_i(t)$ will become equal to $\theta_0(t)$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$.

B. Design of the guidance laws

For the i th USV located at $p_i(x_i(t), y_i(t))$, the distance between vehicle and its reference point $\hat{p}_{di} = [\hat{x}_{di}(\theta_0), \hat{y}_{di}(\theta_0)]^T$, in the path-tangential reference frame, is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_{ei} \\ y_{ei} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \alpha_i & -\sin \alpha_i \\ \sin \alpha_i & \cos \alpha_i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_i - \hat{x}_{di} \\ y_i - \hat{y}_{di} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where x_{ei} and y_{ei} represents the along-track and cross-track error, whereas $\alpha_i = \text{atan}(\hat{y}'_{di}(\theta_0)/\hat{x}'_{di}(\theta_0))$ is a path-tangential angle (see Fig 1). Differentiating x_{ei} and y_{ei} along (1) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_{ei} &= U_i \cos(\psi_i - \alpha_i) \cos \beta_i - U_i \sin(\psi_i - \alpha_i) \sin \beta_i - U_{pi}, \\ \dot{y}_{ei} &= U_i \sin(\psi_i - \alpha_i) \cos \beta_i + U_i \cos(\psi_i - \alpha_i) \sin \beta_i, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\beta_i = \text{atan}(v_i/u_i)$ represents the sideslip angle, $U_i = \sqrt{u_i^2 + v_i^2}$ is the total USV speed, and U_{pi} is the velocity of the virtual reference point relative to $\{n\}$:

$$U_{pi} = \dot{\theta}_0 \sqrt{(\hat{x}'_{di})^2 + (\hat{y}'_{di})^2} \approx \dot{\theta}_i \sqrt{(\hat{x}'_{di})^2 + (\hat{y}'_{di})^2}, \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{x}'_{di}(\theta_0) = \partial \hat{x}_{di} / \partial \theta_0$ and $\hat{y}'_{di}(\theta_0) = \partial \hat{y}_{di} / \partial \theta_0$.

In order to meet the requirements of the objective in (3), it follows from (8) that it is sufficient to ensure that $y_{ei} \rightarrow 0$ and $x_{ei} \rightarrow 0$ for each vehicle. To minimize the cross-track error, we employ the following integral line-of-sight (ILOS) heading guidance law [14]:

$$\psi_{di} = \alpha_i(\theta_0) - \arctan\left(\frac{y_{ei} + \sigma_i y_{\text{int},i}}{\Delta_i}\right), \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{y}_{\text{int},i} = \frac{\Delta_i y_{ei}}{(y_{ei} + \sigma_i y_{\text{int},i})^2 + \Delta_i^2}, \quad (12)$$

where Δ_i represents the look-ahead distance, $\sigma_i > 0$ is the integral constant, and $y_{\text{int},i}$ denotes the integrator state used to compensate for the sideslip angle. Using the integrator state, the sideslip angle is estimated as $\hat{\beta}_i = \sigma_i y_{\text{int},i} / \Delta_i$. On the other hand, the along-track error is minimized using the following surge guidance law:

$$u_i = U_{pi} \cos \hat{\beta}_i - \xi_{1i} \tanh(\xi_{2i} x_{ei}), \quad (13)$$

where ξ_{1i} and ξ_{2i} are positive constants.

From (13), one can conclude that upon reaching the reference position (i.e., $x_{ei} = 0$), the vehicle's surge velocity becomes equal to $U_{pi} \cos \hat{\beta}_i$, meaning that U_i will converge to U_{pi} . To prevent excessively large speeds, \tanh function is employed due to its property of saturation for large values of $\xi_{2i} x_{ei}$ [14], [18].

The heading guidance laws (11)-(12), along with the surge guidance laws (13), will enforce the followers to maintain the desired position within the convex hull spanned by the virtual leaders.

Fig. 2: Communication topology between the USVs and virtual leaders with $F = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, $L = \{5, 6, 7\}$.

Fig. 3: Containment path following performance.

Fig. 4: Estimation of desired reference paths.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, numerical simulations are presented to verify the effectiveness of the proposed distributed guidance algorithm for containment maneuvering. We consider a networked USV system composed of four followers $F = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and three leaders $L = \{5, 6, 7\}$. The communication topology is depicted in Fig. 2.

For each USV the heading controller is modeled as in [19], while the surge velocity is assumed to be perfectly controlled. The virtual leaders' path information is given by $p_5 = [\theta(t), A \sin(\omega\theta(t))]^T$, $p_6 = [\theta(t), A \sin(\omega\theta(t)) - 40]^T$, and $p_7 = [\theta(t) - 90, A \sin(\omega(\theta(t) - 90)) - 20]^T$, where $A = 25m$ and $\omega = 9 \times 10^{-3}$ rad/s. The other parameters are selected as follows: $\nu_s = 3$, $v_i = 0.3m/s$, $\Delta_i = 10m$, $\gamma = 0.2s^{-1}$, $\sigma_i = 1m$, $\xi_{1i} = 0.8m/s$, and $\xi_{2i} = 0.1m^{-1}$.

Fig. 3 shows the reference and actual paths of the vehicles, as well as the virtual leaders' paths. It can be observed that the USVs follow the reference paths while staying within the convex hull spanned by the leaders. Fig. 4 depicts the desired and estimated reference paths. It can be seen that the consensus algorithm (5) successfully ensures that the actual reference paths closely follow the exact ones determined by

(d) The total velocities of the USVs and their reference points.
 Fig. 5: Quantitative metrics for algorithm performance.

Eq. (4). The along-track and cross-track errors are depicted in Fig. 5a and Fig. 5b, respectively. Notably, both errors converge to zero, implying that each vehicle closely follows its reference point despite the presence of ocean currents. From Fig. 3, it is evident that the vehicles courses make a slight deviation from the path direction, indicating effective compensation for the sideslip angle. Additionally, Fig. 5c illustrates the estimated and actual sideslip angles, showing how the estimated values smoothly approach the true ones. Finally, Fig. 5d shows the resultant velocity of USVs and velocities of the reference points. It can be seen that after approximately 150s, each vehicle moves at its reference point velocity U_{pi} .

V. CONCLUSION

A distributed guidance method for containment maneuvering of a fleet of underactuated USVs is proposed in this paper. Numerical simulations confirm its effectiveness, demonstrating that USVs can follow a reference path contained within the convex hull spanned by multiple virtual leaders, even in the presence of ocean currents. Future work

will focus on analyzing the stability of the overall system and improving the proposed method by taking communication delays into account.

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